

COMPOUNDS OF ANTIMONY TRICHLORIDE WITH PHENOLS AND NITROPHENOLS

BY SARJU PRASAD AND SURESH KUMAR

Several compounds of antimony have been prepared by refluxing a mixture of antimony trichloride and a phenol or a nitrophenol in organic solvents, their properties studied and their structures discussed.

The reaction of antimony trichloride with water results in the formation of antimony oxychloride, which shows that one of the chlorine atoms is differently and more stably attached to antimony than the remaining two, which are detached from the molecule. A review of literature shows that similar behaviour has been observed in the reaction between antimony trichloride and phenols, when only two chlorine atoms are replaced by the mobile hydrogen atoms of the hydroxy groups of the phenol, the remaining one remaining intact.

Causse (*Compt. rend.*, 1897, 125, 954) obtained antimony catechol chloride by the action of catechol on an aqueous solution of antimony trichloride. Certain other phenols yielded similar derivatives, which were amorphous and readily dissociated by cold alcohol.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of compounds obtained by the action of phenol or nitrophenol on antimony trichloride in organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenols and nitrophenols used were of B.D.H. or Merck's "Pure" and antimony trichloride of "Extra pure" quality. The solvents were dehydrated and redistilled.

Antimony trichloride and phenol or nitrophenol solutions in organic solvents were mixed in certain molar ratio, depending upon the number of hydroxy groups present in the phenol. It was refluxed on an oil-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. The compound formed was extracted with a suitable solvent to remove the excess of the reactants, dried and analysed. Two sets of experiments, taking in one antimony trichloride and in the other phenol or nitrophenol in excess, were carried out simultaneously. The results reported are an average of the two values.

Antimony was estimated as Sb_2S_3 , chlorine as $AgCl$ and the organic matter, found by difference.

TABLE I

Phenols.	Compounds formed.	Colour.	M.P.	%Antimony. Found.	%Chlorine. Calc.	%Org. matter. Found.	%Org. matter. Calc.		
Monohydroxy phenols.									
α -Naphthol	Antimony di- α -naphthol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$.	Light blue	80°	27.64	27.46	8.24	8.01	64.12	64.53
β -Naphthol	Antimony di- β -naphthol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O})_2$.	Pink	78°	27.16	27.46	7.98	8.01	64.86	64.53
Hydroquinone	Antimony di-hydroquinone chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3\text{O})_2$.	Orange-yellow	160°	30.13	30.19	8.71	8.80	61.16	61.01
Dihydroxyphenols.									
Phenolphthalein	Antimony phenolphthalein chloride. $\text{SbCl}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CO})_2\cdot(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})_2$.	Dirty white	230°	25.67	25.72	7.55	7.50	66.78	66.78
Resorcinol	Antimony resorcinol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_2$.	Red-brown	103°	46.05	45.90	13.26	13.38	40.69	40.72
Trihydroxyphenols.									
Pyrogallol	Tri-antimony di-pyrogallol chloride. $3 \text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3)_2$.	Brownish pink	240° (decomp.)	53.16	53.26	15.43	15.53	31.41	31.21
Phloroglucinol	Tri-antimony di-phloroglucinol chloride. $3 \text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3)_2$.	Brown-black	85° (decomp.)	53.18	53.26	15.49	15.53	31.33	31.21
Nitrophenols.									
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	Antimony di- <i>m</i> -nitrophenol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2\text{O})_2$.	Dirty powder	114°	28.22	28.10	8.15	8.19	63.63	63.71
<i>p</i> - " "	Antimony di- <i>p</i> -nitrophenol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2\text{O})_2$.	Yellowish	130°	27.98	28.10	8.10	8.19	63.90	63.71
2 : 4 Di- " "	Antimony di-2 : 4-dinitrophenol chloride. $\text{SbCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2\text{NO}_2\text{O})_2$.	Yellow powder	100°	23.34	23.26	6.59	6.78	70.07	69.95

DISCUSSION

From the results it is evident that one molecule of antimony trichloride reacts with two molecules of a monohydroxy and one molecule of a dihydroxy phenol and three molecules of antimony trichloride react with 2 molecules of a

trihydroxy phenol. Nitro- and dinitrophenols give similar results, only the hydroxy group being affected. The compounds formed can be represented as:

in the case of mono-, di- and trihydroxy phenols respectively.

The compounds have low melting points and are soluble in most of the organic solvents. On boiling with water or sodium hydroxide, antimony oxychloride and the respective phenol or sodium phenate are formed.

The stability of these derivatives towards water, sodium hydroxide and mineral acids is as dihydroxy phenol > monohydroxy phenol > trihydroxy phenol.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

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